

CHANGES IN LITERARY CRITICISM

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Abstract. *In the period of independence, under the influence of national ideology, the fields of science and education have been reformed. First of all, attention has been paid to the field of literary and artistic criticism, the study of its current issues, and the change of the critic's outlook has become important. The methodology and philosophical basis of literary criticism have changed. Today's critical worldview, way of thinking, and concepts are getting richer in harmony with the aesthetics and art of the world. Literary criticism always monitors how the essence and psyche of a person is illuminated.*

Keywords: *criticism, artistic text, poetics, critic, style, analysis.*

Introduction.

In the years of independence, the study of cultural heritage, the feeling of national pride and the understanding of values, getting deeper into the essence of literary studies, justifying the worthy place of artistic works in the development of literature, and observing the activities of creators who had a strong influence on the literature of the present time, have intensified. The interpretation of universal ideas in fiction has a positive effect on the future of the mature generation. Changes in the poetic originality of the work, the scope of the image, and the compositional integrity are considered to be the product of changes in the artist's thinking. Studying examples of works created in literary studies is important in enriching artistic thinking. A literary critic consistently studies the literary process, the individual style and skill of the author, and puts forward his philosophical and moral views. "Literature continues to live as an artistic phenomenon, as the main sphere of human mental and psychological activity, as a visual representation of the universe. Only it should be a literature enriched with the newest and most advanced ideas of the time, national ideas, and most importantly, it should be artistically high. The literature of independent nation must be a literature of a very high standard in all respects" [1].

Main part.

The variety of methods and styles of analysis chosen by the critic is important. After all, the level of effectiveness and readability of a work of criticism depends, in fact, on the appeal of the same method and style. In the experience of literary criticism, sociological research of artistic analysis, structural analysis or comparative (comparative-historical, comparative-typological) detailed analysis of the text of the work and other forms of analysis are found. A new approach to the analysis of a work of art, mastering the subtle points of the creator's vision, the layers of meaning under the words, allows one to understand the true essence. If the critic discovers and understands the phenomenon that the creator wants to express, the goal will be achieved. When evaluating a work of art, the critic's experienced look and bold judgment interprets the novelty, rationality of the poet's or writer's views, how they connect the components in the artistic study of life.

In the process of critical analysis, the critic shows the harmony of folklore and classical tradition in the way of poetic expression of the work, directs it to a specific goal, makes appropriate use of theoretical sources, relies on comparative observation, and tries to draw scientific conclusions. The critic remembers the importance of the method of comparison in clarifying the

poetic thought, making the image bright and lively. A critic observes various life events that occur in the spiritual world of a person and achieves the deepest possible perception of the change in their psyche.

The principles of renewal in criticism of the period of independence are comprehensive, which motivated for a deep understanding of important methodological foundations, the study of the process and factors of renewal in the thinking of literary criticism, requiring the acquisition of research in the literary process based on various approaches and methods in the context of the reevaluation of cultural heritage, in particular, Uzbek literature of the 20th century, mastering the principles of approaching the issue from the point of view of national values. At the same time, the critic realized that researching various forms and styles in the literary process on the basis of new criteria of artistry has become an important issue. In criticism, it has become important to base the artist's talent, knowledge, culture, leadership on the mind of the reader, and observe his literary and aesthetic requirements.

Rarely talented critics and their works prove that literary criticism is a special kind of creativity, a field of science. Literature and art help the development of society by affecting the heart and mind of a person with their own means of imagery in the artistic assimilation of life and reality. Literary criticism, like art, naturally affects the development of the personality and the development of thinking due to the fact that it fulfills this task. The very nature of critical works requires them to be works of art. For this, the critic who thinks about the work of art must be an artist himself. However, the extent to which a literary critic is an artist and the manner in which he or she discusses it are of particular value. Artistic mastering of life, presenting it with images and impressive motives increases the responsibility of the artist.

In the literary process, the principle of describing life in accordance with the rules of beauty, and reflecting a person's character in its true nature is gaining strength rather than raising issues, reflecting social events, depicting an ideological person. Writers pay attention to the issue of glorifying noble virtues and poetizing the elegance of the world, along with personal tragedy and inferiority complex. An important factor is the evaluation of the social attitude from the hero's point of view, the determination of the correct approach to the problem situation, and the implementation of new ideas in the chapter of continuation of cultural traditions. When creating an individual image of a character, it is desirable to deeply illuminate his moral, philosophical views, world of thought.

A literary critic closely observes the trinity of the writer, literary text, and reader, their harmony. This inextricable connection grounds the illumination of many aspects of literary studies, criticism, aesthetics, and psychology. "There is an internal movement, a transition from one to another, a transfer process in the writer-artistic text-reader relationship, which is known as artistic communication. Gives rise to artistic communication, psychology of creativity, aesthetics of artistic perception; semiotics and structuralism; literary, artistic criticism, critic; the theory of interpretation (hermeneutics), evaluation (axiology) of the work" [2].

In the Uzbek criticism of the period of independence, biographical, historical, ontological, and genetic approach to the work of art is strengthened. Mental and spiritual purification encourages to feel the art, to understand the secrets of the artistic world. The widespread use of the biographical method in criticism clarifies the idea of the author's creative laboratory, and makes one aware of the secrets of the process of writing a work. Studying the work of art in conjunction with the creator's personality, spiritual and educational world allows to identify the necessary and

useful information. The critic takes into account the important signs of the artist's psychology and personality when illuminating his work.

The teaching of interpreting the meaning of an artistic text is called hermeneutics. When a critic creates a work about a work, he interprets the layers of the main meaning and evaluates the apparent content objectively. The critic gives an impartial assessment of the work of art by means of various methods of analysis and approaches. Researching the works of art that have become a phenomenon in the history of literature from the aspect of historicity makes it possible to shed light on the views on poetic images, language features, and the ideal of the creator. In criticism, the analysis of works based on a historical approach implies the study of leading trends and problems specific to the literature of a certain period.

A work of art is a product of art that affects the human psyche. The tone of words, the mystery of meanings are directed to the deep expression of various situations. Illuminating the image and character of the hero, conveying the evolution in it requires a fine taste and high potential from the creator. In the current process of globalization, human destiny is becoming more complicated. The worldview of people under the influence of information and communication is changing day by day. In artistic creation, figurative images, integration of sciences, harmony between arts, mythological scenes, derivatives regarding the macro and micro world are increasing. Art samples are being created based on religious and secular teachings about the unity of man with flora and fauna. The critic explores the art of the text through a careful analysis of new images and nuances in the literary process.

Conclusion.

The life-giving principles in the criticism of the independence period have become important, gaining a deep understanding of the principles that appeared in it, studying the process and factors of renewal in literary criticism, requiring the study of the researches that took place in the literary process based on different approaches and methods regarding the re-evaluation of the cultural heritage, in particular, the Uzbek literature of the 20th century, mastering the principles of approach to the problem from the point of view of national values, and at the same time the research of various forms and styles in the literary process based on new criteria of artistry have become important issues.

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